

STAKEHOLDERS PERSPECTIVE ON CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY: MINING AND COMMUNITY SYNERGY

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ABSTRACT

The study examines stakeholder's perspective on corporate social responsibility in Bunawan, Agusan del Sur, from the perspective of stakeholders. CSR is evaluated across economic, legal, ethical, and philanthropic responsibilities, while community development focuses on health, education, livelihood, public utilities, and socio-cultural aspects. Using a convergent parallel design, the study employed a mixed-method approach and surveyed 366 respondents from the two barangays, Libertad and Consuelo. Findings reveal stakeholders' perceptions of CSR implementation: economic responsibility scored 4.38, legal responsibility 4.65, ethical responsibility 4.48, and philanthropic responsibility 4.56. Similarly, the impact on community development received high ratings, with health at 4.50, education at 4.45, livelihood at 4.37, public utilities at 4.49, and socio-cultural at 4.58, all indicating "very satisfactory" results. Significant differences were found in the level of CSR implementation but not in its impact on community development. Additionally, a significant relationship exists between CSR implementation and its impact on community development. These findings highlight the effectiveness of CSR initiatives in positively influencing community development and emphasize the importance of continued stakeholder engagement in shaping CSR strategies for sustainable outcomes.

Keywords: *Community development, Corporate social responsibility*

INTRODUCTION

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) refers to the corporate responsibility of providing activities or programs to the community and the environment in all their operations (Amoako 2016). CSR is a mandate for a mining corporation to provide programs to its community as their continuing commitment as a responsible member of society in contributing to economic development and the environment in all aspects of their operations of mining corporation (League of Corporate Foundations, 2010). Thus, CSR is crucial in addressing social and environmental concerns stemming from mining operations, highlighting the need for sustainable interactions that benefit within the community (Boutilier & Thomson, 2011).

In connection to above preceding concepts, the Philippine mining industry has increasingly focused on CSR initiatives, including community development, environmental protection, respect for indigenous peoples' rights, and its transparency (NEDA, 2021). According to Kumari, Schrawat, and Sharma (2016), that there has been a positive impact of the foundation's CSR of Anbuja Cement Ltd., the leading cement companies in India, on the community towards education, scholarship, youth care program, cultural program, and other socio-economic aspects of the community. Wherein the CSR framework of mining industry is suited to the local suitability in order to provide financial and non-financial support to the community needs (Sering, 2014). Moreover, CSR practices has been tailored to suit the unique socio-economic and environmental contexts of developing countries, and how these practices can potentially mitigate negative impacts while promoting sustainable development (Muthuri & Gilbert, 2018).

Based on Cities and Municipalities Competitiveness Index and the Department of Trade and Industry for the year 2022 revealed the Agusan del Sur is highlighted as one of the poorest municipalities in the Philippines. It has consistently ranked among the Top 10 poorest municipalities. The Caraga Region, including Agusan del Sur, posted a high poverty incidence among families, with a rate of 33.4 percent in 2021, indicating widespread economic challenges and disparities. The municipality of Bunawan, Agusan del Sur, holds a low socio-economic ranking compared to other municipalities in the Philippines. It ranked 455th out of 512 1st to 2nd Class Municipalities in terms of competitiveness, indicating potential economic challenges and underdevelopment. In addition, the government's efficiency in providing essential services like Health and Education in Bunawan is also a concern. The rankings of 37 and 78 for these services suggest that there might be issues related to capacity and quality in these areas. Despite the presence of established studies on CSR in other locations, there is a lack of research conducted specifically in Bunawan, Agusan Del Sur. This gap in research indicates a need to understand the local context and potential challenges unique to the locality.

The conduct of this study on Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) in Bunawan, Agusan del Sur holds significant implications for both the local community and the broader understanding of sustainable development practices, have the potential to drive positive change in the municipality and contribute to the advancement of responsible business practices within the mining industry.

Research Questions

This study aims to determine the Impact of the Corporate Social Responsibility programs of Philsaga Mining Corporation on community development in its immediate proximate locality. The findings of which serve as the basis for proposing intervention schemes.

Specifically, it seeks to attain the following objectives:

1. What is the level of implementation towards the corporate social responsibility of mining corporations as perceived by the stakeholders in terms of:
 - 1.1 Economic Responsibility;
 - 1.2 Legal Responsibility;
 - 1.3 Ethical Responsibility; and
 - 1.4 Philanthropic Responsibility?
2. What is the level of impact on community development through corporate social responsibility of mining corporations as perceived by the stakeholders in terms of:
 - 2.1 Health;
 - 2.2 Education;
 - 2.3 Livelihood;
 - 2.4 Public Utilities; and
 - 2.4 Socio-Cultural?
3. What are the problems encountered by stakeholders in the implementation of corporate social responsibility of mining corporations?
4. Is there a significant difference in the level of Implementation towards the corporate social responsibility of mining corporation as perceived by respondents from identified barangays of Bunawan, Agusan del Sur?
5. Is there a significant difference in the level of Impact of community development through corporate social responsibility of mining corporation as perceived by respondents from identified barangays of Bunawan, Agusan del Sur?
6. Is there a significant relationship between the level of implementation of mining corporation's social responsibility and its level of impact on community development as perceived by respondents from identified barangays of Bunawan, Agusan del Sur?
7. Based on the findings, what intervention can be proposed?

METHODOLOGY

Research Locale

The study was conducted in the Municipality of Bunawan, Agusan Del Sur where the Philsaga Mining Corporation is situated. Bunawan has 10 barangays which the two (2) barangays are the respondents on the study, barangay Consuelo and Libertad these based on the highest and lowest allocated annual budget of CSR programs of Philsaga Mining Corporation.

Major participants in the Philippine mining industry, particularly in gold extraction and processing, are found in Agusan del Sur which is located at Caraga in region XIII. According to provincial mineral profile of 2019 one of the major economic activities is gold mining which greatly contributes to its GDP. This consists of a refinery operated by Mindanao Mineral Processing and Refining Corporation as well as a leading gold mine run by Philsaga Mining Corporation. These establishments have significant economic impacts such that they contributed 16.8% to total GRDP or PHP17.74 billion.

As per December 2019, mining industry investment stood at PHP7.67 billion for the province. Gross output values of gold ore extraction and processing were valued at PHP7.14 billion and PHP7.32 billion respectively. Majority of this went into export mainly to Hong Kong, with estimated earnings amounting to US\$137.87 million last year. And with this, the mining sector of Agusan del Sur demonstrates its commitment to environmental preservation and social development besides economic gains. Beneficiaries included 35 barangays where Philsaga Mining Corporation allocated Php 27.06 million for host and surrounding communities.

There are many jobs provided by mining (5,196 people worked there as of 2019) despite it occupying just 0.25% of the provincial land area. In relation to mining, the province prioritizes responsible mineral development that aims at striking a balance between community welfare, environmental sustainability and economic advancement

Research Respondents

The respondents of the study were the household community stakeholders using purposive random sampling in which the two (2) barangays are the highest and lowest budget allocation among the 10 barangays based on the five (5) year's Annual report of SDMP's Philsaga Mining in Agusan del Sur. For every family household, there must be one (1) responder who must be at least 18 years old and a bona fide resident of the relevant barangay (as defined in Presidential Degree No. 431 sec. 4 who has lived in the

barangay for at least six months). Then, to acquire population sample size, the researcher made use of stratified random sampling technique.

To acquire data in the qualitative analysis, the researcher made use of purposive random sampling; they were the key informants lived there since birth or categorized as “lumads”, having more depth insights and thoughts with regards on the CSR programs of Philsaga Mining Corporation. There were five (5) key informants per barangay in this study.

Table 1
Distribution of Respondents

Barangay	Population (Household)	Sample Size
Consuelo	2, 597	220
Libertad	1,714	146
Total	4,311	366

Research Instrument

The study utilized an adapted-modified questionnaire based on the survey conducted by Sering, (2014) “Corporate Social Responsibility of Two Mining Companies in Surigao del Sur, Philippines” and the community perspective tool of Alexander Asumah (2015) “Effects of Corporate Social Responsibility on Community Development: A Case Study of Anglogold Ashanti Obuasi Mine.”

The researcher was able to modify the indicators of the above-mentioned adopted questionnaire to fit in with the foregoing scenarios in the research locale. The corporate social responsibility questionnaire initially included four criteria: economic responsibility, legal responsibility, philanthropic responsibility, and ethical responsibility. On the other hand, the corporate social programs initially included five areas: education, health, livelihood, public utilities, and socio-cultural.

The instrument comprises four (4) Parts: Part 1 is for socio-economic profile of the respondent; Part II is for the stakeholders perception on the level of implementation of corporate social responsibility of mining corporation; Part III is for the level of impact to community development through corporate social responsibility of mining corporations as perceived by the stakeholders; Part IV is for interview guide questions with four (4) questions made to key informants about the impact of CSR and the problems encountered by stakeholder in the implementation of CSR. In Part II, the researcher modified/rephrased all the items in ethical responsibility. For economic responsibility, item 2 was modified and the rest questions were adapted. For legal responsibility, items 4 and

5 were modified by the researcher and the rest of the items were adapted. For philanthropic responsibility, the researcher modified all the statements. In Part III, community ratings on corporate social programs, the researcher modifies/ rephrased all the indicators of health, education, livelihood, public utilities, and socio-cultural. Since the survey questionnaire is adapted-modified is it subject to validity test.

Content validation was done beforehand to ensure that the instruments were ready before the launch. The instrument was validated by a faculty member College of Arts and Sciences of Agusan Del Sur State University with 35 years of experience both in research and teaching and as a researcher consultant in Agusan Del Sur. An Executive Director of Institute for Peace and Development in Mindanao with 18 years of experience in academe and as a University Adviser of the MSU-President and researcher coordinator in Mindanao State University, Marawi City. A government employee under DENR- Agusan Del Sur designated as an Environmental Management Specialist II with 9 years of experience. The researcher asks the approval of expert to validate the questionnaire by sending letter and reaching them through chats and email. After content validation, the researcher conducted a reliability test by conducting pilot testing on individuals who were not part of the respondents. The results of the reliability test are shown in the appendices. Finally, seek out for approval to all panelist on the final float of the survey questionnaire. Likewise, for the interview guide questions.

Furthermore, the study is intended to use the Likert scale points in the survey questionnaire.

For Part II, the following scaling procedures are to be used.

Scale	Description	Interpretation
5	Very Satisfactory	The respondent involved in the indicator noted very satisfactory with the statement that these CSR programs are implemented by the company
4	Satisfactory	The respondent involved in the indicator noted satisfactory with the statement that these CSR programs are implemented by the company
3	Don't know	The respondent involved in the indicator noted is Don't Know with the statement that these CSR programs are neither or nor likely implemented by the company.
2	Unsatisfactory	The respondent involved in the indicator noted is unsatisfactory with the statement that these CSR programs are not likely implemented by the company

The hypothetical mean range used to interpret the weighted average definitively (Pimentel, 2010).

Scale	Range of WM	Description
5	4.51-5.00	Very Satisfactory
4	3.51-4.50	Satisfactory
3	2.51-3.50	Don't know
2	1.51-2.50	Unsatisfactory
1	1.00-1.50	Very Unsatisfactory

For Part III, the following scaling procedures are to be used.

Scale	Range of WM	Description	Interpretation
(5) Severe - S	4.51-5.00	Very High	Major long-term impact
(4) Major - MA	3.51-4.50	High	Major short-term impact
(3) Moderate- MO	2.51-3.50	Moderate	Significant impact
(2) Minor- MI	1.51-2.50	Low	Short-term impact
(1) Insignificant- I	1.00-1.50	Very low	Minimal Impact

Data Gathering Procedure

After the research instrument validation and reliability test, the researcher followed the data gathering procedure.

First, the researcher personally hand- in the approval letter to Barangay Libertad and Consuelo containing the purpose of the study. After, granting permission, on the next day I prepared for an orientation to my research team for the upcoming survey.

Next, the researchers proceed to an actual survey within the two (2) barangays (Libertad and Consuelo) and we split into two (2) groups. Then, the researchers were administered on conducting and collecting the survey questionnaire. On the Part IV, interview guide questions, initial survey was conducted to all respondents. Afterwards we identified the ten (10) Key informants among the 366 respondents to undergone depth

interview using purposive random sampling. Then, another interview session for the Key informants. Actual one-on-one interviews were conducted with the key informants to collect data. The researcher used a non-directive style of interview using open-ended questions, allowing the participants the freedom to control the pacing and subject matter of the interview. Additionally, upon conducting interviews, the researcher recorded the conversation as stated in the written consent and discussed during the orientation phase, and additional sub-questions were asked as needed. Answers to the interviews were recorded.

Finally, all the gathered survey questionnaires were tallied and tabulated on the excel form in preparation for the data analysis. For the quantitative analysis, it used different statistical tools such as mean, one-way Anova, and Pearson correlation for interpretation of the data results. On the other note, for qualitative analysis it used a thematic Analysis. This would be used to treat qualitative data to analyze the interview data. Inductive coding was conducted by directly reading the data, accompanied by deductive coding (Hennink et al., 2020), and closely examining the interview data collected from the key informants. Depending on the content of the transcription, a phrase or a paragraph would be the unit of analysis during opening coding. The researcher reviewed all the transcriptions word-for-word, annotated the data, observed the repetitions, noted the topic changes, and investigated the underlying concepts to construct the inductive codes in this study. Selective coding was then used to improve the categories and create a narrative that links them.

Statistical Treatment

The researcher used the following statistical tools were able to analyze and interpret the data the:

Mean. This would be used for problems 1 and 2 of the study to be specific on the extent of stakeholders' perspective towards community development and its impact and level of implementation of CSR.

One- way ANOVA. This would be used for problems 4 and 5 of the significant difference of stakeholders' perspective towards community development and its impact and level of implementation of CSR.

Pearson's Correlation. This would be used for problem 6 to determine the significant relationship between the level of Impact and Implementation of the Corporate Social Responsibility of Mining Corporation in Agusan del Sur to community development.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Table 1
Overall Level of Implementation towards the corporate social responsibility of mining corporation as perceived by the stakeholders

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Description
Economic Responsibility	4.38	Very Satisfactory
Legal Responsibility	4.65	Very Satisfactory
Ethical Responsibility	4.48	Very Satisfactory
Philanthropic Responsibility	4.56	Very Satisfactory
Over All Mean	4.52	Very Satisfactory

Table 1 reveals that the overall mean of 4.52 as very satisfactory suggests that, on average, the stakeholders perceive the corporate social responsibility (CSR) implementation of the mining corporation very positively. This indicates a high level of satisfaction among stakeholders regarding the corporation's efforts across all CSR indicators. This reflects a strong commitment by the corporation towards fulfilling its social responsibilities, encompassing economic, legal, ethical, and philanthropic aspects. And its positive perception is crucial for maintaining stakeholder trust and enhancing the corporation's reputation in the community and the industry.

Moreover, the highest mean, observed in the category of Legal Responsibility, with a mean of 4.65 as very satisfactory, indicates that stakeholders perceive the corporation's adherence to legal standards and regulations as exceptionally satisfactory. This suggests that the corporation is diligent in complying with relevant laws governing its operations, which is essential for maintaining legality, mitigating risks, and upholding ethical business practices. A high rating in legal responsibility reflects a robust legal framework within the corporation, contributing to its overall corporate governance and risk management strategies.

Although still rated as "very satisfactory, the lowest mean among the indicators is observed in Economic Responsibility, with a score of 4.38. While this indicates a positive perception by stakeholders regarding the corporation's economic impact, it also suggests that there may be areas for improvement. Stakeholders might perceive certain aspects of economic responsibility, such as job creation, local economic development, or resource management, to be slightly less satisfactory compared to other CSR indicators. Addressing any concerns related to economic responsibility can further enhance stakeholder satisfaction and contribute to the corporation's overall CSR performance and reputation.

The interpretation of those results means indicates that while the stakeholders perceive the corporation's CSR efforts positively overall, there are specific areas of strength and potential areas for improvement. The corporation should continue to prioritize legal compliance, maintain its high standards in ethical conduct, and further enhance its economic impact and philanthropic initiatives to ensure holistic CSR performance and sustain stakeholder satisfaction over the long term. Regular assessment and proactive measures to address stakeholder feedback can help the corporation maintain its positive reputation and contribute positively to society and the environment.

The findings are strengthened by the study of Ansu-Mensah et al. (2021) which give emphasize on the critical importance of CSR in mining, underlining its role in mitigating adverse effects, fostering sustainable development, and nurturing positive relationships with local communities and stakeholders. The extractive nature of mining poses unique challenges and opportunities, making CSR indispensable for responsible resource management and sustainable operations (Yulianita et al. 2018). Moreover, amidst escalating scrutiny from NGOs, social movements, and indigenous groups, mining companies are increasingly pressed for greater transparency and accountability. In addition, Adorador (2019) emphasizes the significance of responsible management of social and environmental impacts, stakeholder engagement, and integration of socially responsible practices within mining organizations. Environmental initiatives, as outlined by Liccud-ambeguia (2023), focus on reducing greenhouse gas emissions, minimizing waste, and conserving water resources.

As pointed out by Yousefian et al. (2023), navigating the landscape of CSR in mining requires a delicate balance between economic, environmental, and social imperatives while addressing stakeholder concerns. Legal and regulatory frameworks vary widely across jurisdictions, demanding careful navigation by mining companies. Transparent and accountable CSR initiatives are imperative to meet stakeholders' expectations for increased transparency and responsibility within the industry.

Table 2
Overall Level of Impact on Community Development through Corporate Social Responsibility of mining corporations as perceived by the stakeholders

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Description
Health	4.50	Very High
Education	4.45	Very High
Livelihood	4.37	Very High
Public Utilities	4.49	Very High
Socio- Cultural	4.58	Very High
Over All Mean	4.48	Very High

Table 2 shows the overall mean of 4.48 that suggests a very high level of impact on community development through CSR initiatives across various domains, as perceived by stakeholders. This indicates that stakeholders view the collective efforts of mining corporations positively in terms of contributing to community development in multiple areas, including health, education, livelihood, public utilities, and socio-cultural aspects.

The highest mean, observed in the socio-cultural domain, with a mean of 4.58 as very high, highlights the effectiveness and significance of CSR initiatives related to promoting cultural preservation, religious support, and socio-cultural empowerment. Stakeholders highly value these initiatives, indicating strong support for cultural heritage and community cohesion. empowerment and socio-economic advancement within the community.

While, the lowest mean among the indicators is observed in the livelihood domain, with a mean of 4.37. While still very high, this suggests slightly less perceived impact compared to other domains. However, it still reflects positive efforts to support economic activities and livelihood opportunities within the community, contributing to poverty alleviation and sustainable development. empowerment and socio-economic advancement within the community. Kurowski and Huk (2021), delineate that CSR in the mining context as encompassing the continuous demonstration of ethical, legal, economic, and philanthropic commitments by mining organizations towards society. Moreover, CSR initiatives remain one way of fostering cordial relationships between host communities and corporations. As such, corporations should be very thorough and deliberate in ensuring that indigenous people are involved in deciding and executing community-based projects, Gabriel and Kobani, (2022)

Social initiatives, including community development, education, and health programs, are also integral components of CSR in mining. Economic considerations, such as local procurement, employment, and sustainable supply chain development, are underscored as essential by Licud-ambeguia (2023). Similarly, the study conducted by Yousefian et al. (2023) delves into the effects of implementing Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) initiatives within the European mining industry. The findings reveal a positive association between CSR performance and economic growth, including profitability and firm value. Particularly, indicators such as training, health & safety, and community development significantly impact economic indicators. These findings provide valuable insights for both scholars and industry experts, aiding in the development of CSR programs tailored to maximize economic returns.

The Challenges Encountered in CSR Implementation

This section discusses the issues encountered by the stakeholders in mining corporation's implementation of corporate social responsibility. The gathered data is based from the common views and opinions of the stakeholders obtained through personal interview.

Economic Responsibility. Respondents were able to appreciate the help of the mining corporation of they have provided to the community. Such acknowledgement is for the employment opportunities, being supportive to community, and able to provide donations to the needy. Respondents have also highlighted the support to community through livelihood projects which provide huge help to every families. Others includes, water system, bridge construction, rubbers, fruits and fertilizers to farmers, free education, and free medical check-up. Contrariwise, financial assistance provided by the company were not able to cater the needs of all. In other words, the company is helpful but not that good enough. As highlighted, the company has selection bias. Especially in providing cash assistance during calamities, they have poor selection process to those who will be given. Families who are really deserving for the help were not able to receive such. Another thing is for the employees. The company has contract issue. This means the contract is not that good, though employees were thankful enough for the job. To strengthened results, various studies explored other means of employment issues.

Likewise, mining has been an active component in decreasing the unemployment rate and providing vital materials to supply chains in other sectors. In some industries, there have not been other substances to replace those that have been exploited from ores, or the technology has not been up to the level to synthesize replaceable elements for them. Based on Knutsen et al. (2017) argue that bribery is increased by mining, as the comparison of an area before and after mining indicates, and it leads to local officials requiring more bribes. However, mining can be beneficial in the sense that it has a direct

impact on the Human Development Index (HDI), corruption reduction, a stable political situation, accountability, the eradication of inequality, and the Gini coefficient (Ericsson, & Löf, 2019).

Thematic Analysis of challenges encountered in CSR implementation as perceived by the key informants. Below are the expressed key informants view regarding economic responsibility:

Perceived Positive Economic Impact

There's somewhat help on development in the community.” (KI 1)

“Very supportive on the community by providing CSR programs.” (KI 3).

“They are helping the economy helps boost the economy.” (KI 5)

“They offer job or livelihood opportunities to people who needed it.” (KI 7).

“Philsaga has greatly contributed to the economy of the barangay through livelihood programs such as the ones they have provided the Black Tinda Wome's Association.” (KI 8).

Insufficient Reach and Support

“They did well on providing programs and projects but still it's not enough.” (KI 2).

“The programs/activities implemented in the area are not very well known in Bunawan.” (KI 6).

“I don't know, I'm not really aware of the programs here in our barangay.” (KI 9)

Selectivity and Fairness in Beneficiary Selection

“It's okay, they helped, but they chose who they help or catered to. They provide a beneficiary list for signatories but few will remain on list only their relatives mostly.” (KI 4).

Infrastructure Development

“They are construct building and Infrastructures.” (KI 10).

Legal Responsibility. As observed by the respondents, CSR programs are not well-known to nearby cities, or other barangays. Clearly, the findings highlight the issue on lack of awareness. This means that most of the people were not aware of the legal responsibilities of the company. There are some who indicates that the company able to

follow the rules and regulations in accordance to the law. More so, only those who are in position or barangay officials are well- informed about such. This further supported by the study of Phiri et al. (2018), examined the interactions of main stakeholders and CSR practices implemented in Zambian copper mining companies. The findings of the study show that there is an explicit power imbalance between civil society and mining firms, which is exacerbated by a number of factors, including conflicts among the primary stakeholders themselves. Furthermore, owing to the lack of a collective consensus for social and environmental frameworks and the eligibility of the leadership of stakeholders through transparency and accountability channels, critical cooperation at the local level is found to be challenging.

Below are the expressed key informants view regarding legal responsibility:

Compliance with legal requirements

“They didn’t violate any laws under mining provisions.” (KI 1).

“They didn’t break any laws or rules because they coordinated with the city.” (KI 2).

“They are responsible of their actions. And they followed the legal procedures.” (KI 5)

“Philsaga follows the appropriate laws in implementing such programs.” (KI 6).

“Good and they adhere to the laws on mining.” (KI 9).

“They did not violate any legal responsibilities.” (KI 10).

Lack of Awareness and Transparency

“I’m not even familiar with CSR initiatives that provided in our barangay.” (KI 3).

“They didn’t do anything wrong and we don’t very aware because only the captain knew.” (KI 4).

Allegation of Legal Violations

“They violated the law by not paying for the contract.” (KI 7).

Perception of Organizational Behavior

“Philsaga may be okay, but some of their workers have big egos.” (KI 8).

Philanthropic Responsibility. PMC is perceived as being helpful to the communities. Specifically, they were able to support activities that would help the community achieved its goal. The company had also provided educational assistance to the students, and scholarship. However, not all deserving families were able to receive help. During calamities, the company provide cash assistance, relief goods, and other means of help but only to those people who are aware of such activity. There are families that are not well- informed.

To support with, Sari and Setiahad (2019), emphasize the demand for transparency and accountability in CSR initiatives, driven by stakeholders seeking greater corporate responsibility from mining companies. Moreover, according to the study of García-Sánchez et al., (2022) emphasizing the importance of transparency which this study warns against the risk of diminishing stakeholder confidence if assessment procedures are not clearly disclosed and executed.

Below are the expressed key informants view regarding philanthropic responsibility:

Positive Impact and Benefits

“That’s good because they were able to help the people.” (KI 1).

“They were able to provide scholarships in the barangays and other nearby municipalities.” (KI 2).

“The people benefited, such as during floods where they received significant help.” (KI 5).

“That good because they help to build infrastructure and building especially such as school buildings and rooms.” (KI 6).

“The PMC support activities that would help the community to achieved its goals.” (KI 7).

“The Philsaga mining corporation established and built water supply facilities within the community. Thus, it was a significant helpful.” (KI 10).

Awareness and Accessibility Issue

“I have nothing to say because we weren’t aware on the programs provided by the PMC.” (KI 3).

“We were not aware if there was anything given by those donations and relief goods for floods and etc.” (KI 4).

“Good for those people who listed and received donations and part of their programs implementations” (KI 8).

“ It is unfair, for those people that doesn’t even knew of those helped by PMC.” (KI 9).

Ethical Responsibility. Respondents acknowledged that the company provide respect to the community especially to the ‘lumad’. The company able to treat lumads in fair manner, and respect their cultures. They also served as the role model in putting up business within community. However, some of the employees of the company affirmed that they have delayed salary, and there are some cases that ethical standard was neglected.

To support with, based on the study conducted by Chaloping (2018), it reveals that social sustainability is intricately linked with community well-being and is influenced by various factors including public policies, ethnic identity, power relations, and territorial claims. And also, emphasizes that social sustainability rooted in values of respect and justice, is a fundamental aspect of sustainable development, driven by the principles of humane treatment and the golden rule.

Below are the expressed key informants view regarding ethical responsibility:

Positive Ethical Practices and Community Respect

“Good that Philsaga is helping the community as to what they can offer.” (KI 3).

“The community was benefited of all the programs.” (KI 4).

“It’s good how the mining company treats the indigenous people and respects their culture.” (KI 7).

“They give respect to the people within the community.”. (KI 9).

“Philsaga has become an example especially among community business owners.” (KI 10).

Ethical Implementation of CSR Programs

“Their implementation of programs is commendable.” (KI 5).

Concerns and Neglect of Ethical Standards

“The employees’ salaries take a long time to be paid.” (KI 1).

“As to ethical there are cases that ethical standards are neglected.” (KI 6).

Equity and Access Issue

“Everything provided by phisaga should be free to all.” (KI 2).

Lack of Awareness and Communication

“We weren’t aware of their ethical responsibilities.” (KI 8).

To highlight things, respondents strongly stressed out issue on work conflicts, limited relief goods and cash assistance, unable to provide seminars and trainings to help small entrepreneurs improved their business, and lack of efforts in disseminating important information.

The findings are similar to the claims of Shirasu & Kawakita (2021). The study stressed that focusing on all stakeholders, not just shareholders, through CSR initiatives can lead to a firm's financial growth in the long run. Education, employment and health for local residents (Mbilima, 2021), cultural and recreational programs (Millington et al., 2019), economic development (Frederiksen, 2019), employee health and safety, environmental protection (Chen et al.,2021) and easier access to finance (Abuya and Odongo, 2020) can occur due to CSR initiatives implemented by mining companies. Although responsible mining cannot be defined in the same way for everyone, mining scenarios can be broadly defined as mining activity that: (1) obtains the consent of local communities before local officials; and (2) conducts a thorough assessment of all potential environmental impacts and risks.

CSR and the Community

Despite of the challenges above stated, respondents have also highlighted the major contributions of the company to community. PMC able to construct roads and make it widened. They have also utilized the use of solar lights, provided water system, donated for building construction such as school building, and health care services. In terms of education, educational programs, educational assistance, transportation services for students- back and forth, and scholarship. During emergencies, they were able to provide ambulance, free medical check-up, provide financial cash assistance during calamities, and even in agriculture such as financing. They provide seedlings to farmers for free, and even provide fruits, rubber, and coconut for livelihood.

To cope up with the challenges and arising issues, respondents were able to provide recommendations for the company to follow and consider. The company must be fair in all, and not one-sided. CRS programs should be expanded. The company may also conduct regular assessment on every households for assessment relevance to the relief goods or any means of help provided by the company. In terms of education, students must be well- assessed to ensure that they are all deserving and that they are financially incapable to support their education. To support with, according to Rela et. al (2020), the study findings highlight that CSR initiative contribute to enhancing community collective efficacy, promoting community action, and facilitating adaptation to challenges brought about by mining activities. Further, emphasizing the importance of transparency which this study warns against the risk of diminishing stakeholder confidence if assessment procedures are not clearly disclosed and executed (García-Sánchez et al., 2022).

Thematic Analysis of CSR contributions to the community as perceived by the key informants. Below are the expressed key informants view regarding CSR contributions to the community:

Livelihood and Economic Support

“They provide livelihood and education programs to the community.” (KI 1).

“They provide water supply and livelihood programs especially to womens and lumads.” (KI 3).

“Grant loan of 30k for farming and operations supports (also for medications).” (KI 5).

“It opens opportunity to the members of community to apply for a job.” (KI 6).

“A big help for the barangay such as street lights, emergency car, and in agriculture sector in providing financial assistance.” (KI 8).

“They also provided livelihood, grocery, refilling station, nursery, health facilities to the communities.” (KI 10).

Educational Support

“They provide livelihood and education programs to the community.” (KI 1).

“Constructed the gym, water refilling stations, scholarships, assistance, facilities, ambulance, trainings, supplies in every barangay.” (KI 7).

Healthcare and Welfare Support

“Conduct feeding program, medical mission in every barangays of bunawan.” (KI 4).

“they also provided livelihood, grocery, refilling station, nursery, health facilities to the communities.” (KI 10).

Infrastructure Development

“Many facilities have been established in our area because of Philsaga.” (KI 2).

“Constructed the gym, water refilling stations, scholarships, assistance, facilities, ambulance, trainings, supplies in every barangay.” (KI 7).

“A big help for the barangay such as street lights, emergency car, and in agriculture sector in providing financial assistance.” (KI 8).

Community Services and Support

“They provide water supply and livelihood programs especially to womens and lumads.” (KI 3).

“For me, even I don’t receive any help but for the community it’s been a substantial.” (KI 9).

“They also provided livelihood, grocery, refilling station, nursery, health facilities to the communities.” (KI 10).

Recommendations

Thematic Analysis of CSR recommendations to the community as perceived by the key informants. Below are the expressed key informants view regarding on recommendations on CSR programs to the community:

Fairness and Inclusivity

“They should be fair and not one-sided. They should listen to all sides of the people regarding contracts/ programs.” (KI 1).

“They should listen to both sides. They shouldn’t be one-sided, they should listen to both sides. People are burdened by laws that the company should be providing.” (KI 2).

“Having fair about the employee’s salary.” (KI 3).

“They should add more programs that benefit the majority, without biased selection or excluding anyone.” (KI 7).

“Everyone can join, they shouldn’t select who can avail.” (KI 8).

Increased and Enhanced Programs Offerings

“They should provide more programs so more people can benefit.” (KI 4).

“Continue to generate possible jobs to help people in the community.” (KI 9).

Targeted Assistance for Vulnerable Groups

“The scholarship assistance should prioritize the poor so they have the opportunity to go to school.” (KI 5).

“Hoping their scholarship prioritize the extremely poor or those needy.” (KI 6).

“When they provide livelihood opportunities, they should select those who are deserving, not just those who are close to them.” (KI 10).

Adverse effects on the environment and society, as a result of the development of the economy cause the need for the implementation of solutions such as CSR, sustainable development, sustainable transport, etc. Although much has been written about what companies should and should not do, the practical implementation of recommendations and requirements is the other side of the coin. All organizations have similar responsibilities towards society, but the type of activity of the company partly determines them. One sector of the economy that raises the most concern in terms of CSR is mining (Straka, 2020; Surówka, 2021; Balog, 2019; Porubčinová, 2020).

Table 3
Significant difference on the level of Implementation towards the Corporate Social Responsibility of a mining corporation as perceived by respondents

Source of Variance	p- value	Decision	Conclusion
Level of Implementation towards the corporate social responsibility of mining corporation as perceived by respondents from identified barangays	0.002	Reject H₀	Sig.

One-way ANOVA: Con, Lib

Analysis of Variance

Source	DF	SS	MS	F	P
Factor	1	0.1511	0.1511	11.33	0.002
Error	38	0.5070	0.0133		
Total	39	0.6581			

Table shows the analysis of variance to test difference in the level of Implementation towards the corporate social responsibility of Mining Corporation as perceived by the stakeholders. Results revealed F value of (F = 11.33) with probability value of 0.002 which is less than 0.05 level of significance. This means, the null hypothesis is rejected. We then conclude that we have strong evidence against the null hypothesis. In other words, there is measurable difference found in the level of Implementation towards the corporate social responsibility of Mining Corporation.

In the study conducted by García-Sánchez et al., (2022) a novel quantitative index aimed at evaluating the corporate social responsibility (CSR) levels of mine sites was developed. The study underscores the potential of this index to enhance the overall positive impact of the mining industry by improving transparency, stakeholder engagement, and the overall returns of mining projects. Moreover, the study advocates for a relative analysis approach over aggregate values, considering the diverse nature of mining projects influenced by geological factors such as depth, ore body characteristics, and ore grade. Emphasizing the importance of transparency in the application of this index, the study warns against the risk of diminishing stakeholder confidence if assessment procedures are not clearly disclosed and executed. Thus, the study not only presents a comprehensive framework for evaluating CSR performance in the mining sector but also highlights the critical need for transparent and rigorous assessment methodologies to ensure the credibility and effectiveness of such tools.

Table 4
Significant difference on the level of Impact of Community Development through Corporate Social Responsibility of a mining corporation as perceived by respondents

Source of Variance	p- value	Decision	Conclusion
Level of Impact of community development through corporate social responsibility of mining corporation as perceived by respondents from identified barangays	0.295	Accept H₀	No Sig.

One-way ANOVA: im con, im lib

Analysis of Variance

Source	DF	SS	MS	F	P
Factor	1	0.0240	0.0240	1.12	0.295
Error	48	1.0245	0.0213		
Total	49	1.0484			

The table shows the analysis of variance to test difference in the level of Impact of community development through corporate social responsibility of Mining Corporation as perceived by the stakeholders. Results revealed F value of (F = 1.12) with probability value of 0.295 which is not less than 0.05 level of significance. This means, we fail to reject the null hypothesis. We then conclude that we have strong evidence for our null hypothesis. In other words, there is no measurable difference found in the level of Impact of community development through corporate social responsibility of Mining Corporation as perceived by the stakeholders.

Table 5
Significant relationship between the level mining Corporate Social and Level of Impact on Community Development as Perceived by respondent

Source of Variance	p- value	Decision	Conclusion
Level of implementation of mining corporation's social responsibility and its level of impact on community development as perceived by respondents	0.001	Reject H₀	Statistically Sig.

Correlations: im con, im lib

Pearson correlation of im con and im lib = 0.557
P-Value = 0.001

The table shows the relationship between the level of CRS implementation and the community development. The findings revealed r coefficient of ($r = 0.557$) with probability value of ($p = 0.001$). In here, the null hypothesis is rejected. It can also be gleaned from result that implementation of CSR has positive correlation to community development. This directs the same directions for both of the variables. In other words, for every increase in the implementation of CSR of Mining Corporation, then there is corresponding increase on the impact of CSR on community development. Otherwise, for every decrease in the implementation of CSR of Mining Corporation, then there is corresponding decrease on the impact of CSR on community development.

The findings are similar to the study of Licud-ambeguia (2023) which aims to explore the impact of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) practices on Community Resilience (COM-R) within the context of a nickel mining company operating in Indonesia. Rela et al. (2020) investigated the role of CSR practices in a nickel mining company in Indonesia, known for its substantial engagement in CSR initiatives. It reveals that CSR initiatives enhance community collective efficacy, promote community action, and facilitate adaptation to challenges arising from mining activities.

PROPOSED MONITORING AND CONTROL FRAMEWORK FOR PHILSAGA MINING CORPORATION IN RELATION TO THE RESULT OF THE STUDY SDMP FRAMEWORK

Structural Formation, **D**evelop Project Implementation, **M**onitoring and Evaluation,
Project Feedback

Objectives

In partnership with Social Development Management and Program (SDMP) of Philsaga Mining Corporation is suggested to create a framework that help to monitor and control the implemented programs in every beneficiary's barangay. Thus, these objectives provide clear, actionable goals for implementing and maintaining the projects or programs effectively.

Figure 1: SDMP Framework

There are four wide-ranging phases that a project manager should undergo when managing a project: Structural Formation, Development of Project Implementation, Monitoring & Evaluation and Project Feedback. In the *Structural Formation* phase, basic dimensions such as organizational structure, communication channels and initial assessments are established to ensure clarity and readiness. The *Development of Project Implementation* phase is followed by detailed planning, evaluation, budget creation, target location selection; and finally, actual implementation of the project. The *Monitoring & Evaluation* phase is important in terms of tracking progress or monitoring processes generating data reports as well as appraising efficiency and effectiveness impacts and sustainability of a particular project through various methods like performance monitoring. Finally, there is also the *Project Feedback* phase which involves documenting and communicating processes and challenges encountered so as to improve future implementations. This focused approach ensures that projects are properly managed, carried out efficiently and consistently improved.

Structural Formation

In every barangay, effective CSR implementation involves adopting a unique organizational structure or network under the control of SDMP personnel or project manager. By so doing, this model seeks to interact directly with programs and activities whereas local government units act as intermediaries. The supervisory unit for each barangay is comprised of SDMP personnel or project manager who supervises the implementation and evaluation of programs and activities and who report directly to SDMP headquarters. These include assessment reports for plans and projects, supervision of community-based schemes, endorsement of projects or programs, monitoring, appraisal and reporting on all such initiatives. Preliminary assessments are

geared towards identifying necessary or critical programs. Community based committees or coordinators nominated by SDMP units become direct contact persons with communities providing community forums, supporting grassroots endeavors in organizing events, bringing resources to bear on vital issues while monitoring, evaluating, and reporting back. Thus, it is the mediating channel for the barangay office that facilitates program/ activity implementation among other types of support to the communities. It is also responsible for providing requirement like project proposal etc.

Figure 2. SDMP Structural Unit

Develop Project Implementation

This phase involves executing the projects for implementation. Starting from the Planning, project budgeting, target location, selection, Implementation and Monitoring & evaluation (see Figure 3). This section focus on **Selection process** in which selection is one of the important phases to be assessed in order to identify the appropriate beneficiaries of the said programs to be implement. There's a need for an *evaluation selection process* as per community information given by the barangay office with the assistance of committee coordinator. On evaluation process, there are two (2) assessment phase to be conduct. *First*, the initial evaluation assessment where the designated coordinator or community coordinator must do one-on-one interview for verification purposes it takes one (1) week after the submission of all the necessary documents. Then, it takes a week of releasing the list of qualified beneficiaries. *Second*, the final evaluation assessment whereas as it takes two (2) weeks after the releasing of qualified beneficiaries. On this stage, the designated coordinator or community coordinator do an orientation process to discussion the following programs or project, its

coverage, benefits and agreement. Thus, to insure the transparency and effectivity and alignment of the programs.

The selection processes where be guided based on the criteria specified below. All the beneficiaries must submit the following *Eligibility Criteria* and other specified requirements. This is to clarify that it applies only for those programs/projects individually for beneficiaries.

Barangay Certificate of Residency. A Barangay Certificate of Residency is an official document issued by a barangay office, certifying that a person he or she has resided in that barangay for a minimum period of six months.

Certification of Indigency. A Certificate of Indigency is an official document issued by a government authority or social welfare office within the municipality of Bunawan, Agusan Del Sur, to certify that an individual or family is economically disadvantaged or financially needy. This certificate serves as proof of the person's inability to afford basic necessities such as food, shelter, healthcare, and even job.

Barangay Profiling Form. An Individual Profiling Form from respective barangay of Bunawan, Agusan Del Sur serves as a comprehensive document designed to gather vital information about residents or the person/ individual within respective barangay. This form typically includes the personal details such as name, age, gender, and contact information, along with residency specifics like duration of stay in the barangay and housing arrangements. Additionally, it delves into family dynamics, including the names and relationships of household members.

The following are some additional needed requirement as to supporting documents.

Police or NBI Clearance. A one (1) copy of a police clearance or NBI clearance.

Birth Certificate/PSA birth certificate. To submit a one (1) original copy and one (1) photocopy of Birth certificate.

Figure 3. Develop Project Implementation Flow

Monitoring & Evaluation

The section pertains to the monitoring and evaluation phase of the framework. It includes the creation of tools for monitoring on the projects and programs that the PMC provided in Bunawan, Agusan Del Sur. *Monitoring* mean on the projects or programs its status and answers the “what’s going on or where it’s going”. It shows a comprehensive data sheets whereas its already have in SDMP as of the moment. On the areas for evaluation, there’s a need to create a tool that evaluate all of the CSR projects and programs if it still effective or not, using the suggestion tool below (see form 1A). This gives the overall views on the programs/projects that inactive within the respective community in Bunawan, Agusan Del Sur. The **Evaluation** form, consist the following areas on health, education, livelihood, public utilities, and socio-cultural aspects.

Project Feedback

The proposed project feedback mechanism outlined in Form 2A. Form 2A explains how the proposed project feedback mechanism is expected to promote community engagement and participation by holding quarterly meetings in each barangay. The intention is that these gatherings will bring local authorities closer to their constituents and thereby enhance openness and inclusivity in governance. For example, the residents will be able to give suggestions, ask questions or get updates on any of the programs and projects implemented within a given barangay. In this way, not only does it encourage active participation but also it allows stakeholders to address issues collaboratively, identify common goals and set priorities.

Besides that, it serves as an avenue for information sharing where locals are updated on what is happening around them. Generally, it forms a crucial platform for dialogue, cooperation and responsibility between barangay officials as well as members of the society in line with effective local governance that is capable of responding to societal needs.

Form 1A
Evaluation Questionnaire for CSR Programs

No.	Statements	Rating				
		5 Excellent	4 Very Good	3 Good	2 Fair	1 Poor
Health						
1	The company conducts medical missions to various communities. <i>(Ang kompanya nagpahigayon mga medical nga misyon sa lainlaing mga komunidad.)</i>					
2	The company has built healthcare centers in the community. <i>(Nagtukod ang kompanya og mga healthcare center sa komunidad.)</i>					
3	The company provides feeding program activities to malnourished children within the community. <i>(Ang kompanya naghatag ug feeding program activities sa mga malnourished nga bata sulod sa komunidad.)</i>					
4	The company conducts training and seminars on health-related programs. <i>(Ang kompanya nagpahigayon og pagbansay ug mga seminar sa mga programa nga may kalabotan sa kahimsog.)</i>					
5	The company support and donates funds for barangay health office in the community. <i>(Ang kompanya nagsuporta ug nagdonar og pundo para sa barangay health office sa komunidad.)</i>					
Education						

1	The company grants scholarship programs. <i>(Ang kompanya naghatag mga programa sa scholarship.)</i>					
2	The company provides educational and recreational facilities. <i>(Naghatag ang kompanya og mga pasilidad sa edukasyon ug kalingawan.)</i>					
3	The company grants honoraria to volunteer teachers. <i>(Ang kompaniya naghatag ug honoraria sa mga boluntaryong magtutudlo.)</i>					
4	The company provides/donates learning materials such as books, computers, etc. <i>(Ang kompanya naghatag/donar sa mga material sa pagkat-on sama sa mga libro, kompyuter, ug uban pa.)</i>					
5	The company supports to ALS (Alternative Learning System) learners in the community. <i>(Ang kompanya nagsuporta sa ALC learners sa komunidad)</i>					
Livelihood						
1	The company provision of Agri-farm Inputs such as seedlings, fertilizers, feedstuffs, and plant protection products for the farmer sectors in the community. <i>(Ang kompanya naghatag ug agri-farm inputs sama sa seedlings, abono, feedstuffs ug plant protection products para sa mga sector sa mag-uuma sa komunidad.)</i>					
2	The company offers job opportunities to host/neighboring communities. <i>(Nagtanyag ang kompanya og mga oportunidad sa trabaho sap ag-host/kasilinganan nga mga komunidad.)</i>					
3	The company provides livelihood opportunities to host/neighboring communities. Such as support backyard Hog Growers association, provision of rubber seedlings, fishing equipment and motor spare parts trading, <i>(Ang kompanya naghatag ug mga kahigayonan sa panginabuhian sap ag-host/kasilinganan nga mga komunidad sama sa pagsuporta sa backyard hog growers asosasyon, rubber seedlings, fishing equipment ug motor spare parts trading)</i>					
4	The company advocates women empowerment through livelihood support for Water Refilling Station for Women's Association. <i>(Ang kompanya nagpasiugda sa paghatag gahum sa kababayan-an pinaagi sa paghatag og suporta sa water refilling station sa asosasyon sa kababayan-an.)</i>					

5	The company conducts business-related seminars/training. <i>(Ang kompanya nagpahigayon og mga seminar/training nga may kalabotan sa negosyo.)</i>					
Public Utilities						
1	The company constructs/maintains barangay roads and bridges. <i>(Ang kompanya nagtukod/nagmentinar sa mga barangay road ug mga tulay.)</i>					
2	The company provides/repairs water management system in the community. <i>(Ang kompanya naghatag/nag-ayo sa Sistema sa pagdumala sa tubig sa komunidad.)</i>					
3	The company constructs/repairs community facilities such as school buildings, barangay halls, etc. <i>(Ang kompanya nagtukod/nag-ayo sa mga pasilidad sa komunidad sama sa mga school building, barangay hall, ug uban pa.)</i>					
4	The company donates 1 unit of delivery/emergency rescue vehicles to the community. <i>(Ang company midonar ug 1 ka unit sa mga sakyanan ngadto sa kominidad.)</i>					
5	The company provides installation of Street lights. Ang kompanya naghatag og instalasyon sa mga suga sa kadalanan)					
Socio-Cultural						
1	The company supports and donates funds for the community's cultural programs (e.g., Sports Day, Fiesta Day). <i>(Ang kompanya nagsuporta ug nagdonar og pundo para sa mga programa sa kultura sa komunidad (Sports Day, Fiesta Day.)</i>					
2	The company supports to Religious Sectors through donations, providing church equipment's such as chairs and others. <i>(Ang kompanya nag suporta sa mga relihiyosong sector pinaagi sa mga donasyon nga pondo, kagamitan sa simbahan sama sa mga linkuranan ug uban pa.)</i>					
3	The company supports/funds the Bunawan Religious Organization on Moral and Spiritual Recovery Program. <i>(Ang kompanya nagsuporta sa moral ug spiritual recovery program sa buanwan religious organization.)</i>					
4	The company conduct seminar for women empowerment in the community through seminars/workshop and trainings such as					

	organizational management/entrepreneurship and skills development training. <i>(Ang kompanya nagpahigayon og seminar para sa paghatag gahum sa kababayan-an sa komunidad.)</i>					
5	The company helps and provides improvement of Women's Center. <i>(Ang Kompanya nagtabang ug naghatag mga pagpaayo sa Wome's Center.)</i>					

**Form 2A
Activity Program Design**

SDMP QUARTERLY MEETING		
TIME	ACITIVITY	PERSONS INVOLVED
8:00 AM – 8:30 AM	Arrival and Attendance	Community Coordinator
8:31 AM ---9:41 AM	Welcome Address	SDMP Personnel/ Project Manager
9:42 AM – 9:50 AM	Unity Dance	All Participants
9:51 AM –12:00 NN	Presentation on Updates or Quarterly Accomplish Review	Any Philsaga—SDMP Representatives
12:01 PM --- 1:00 PM	Lunch	All Participants
1:01 PM – 2:00 PM	Open Forum and Other Concerns	All Participants
2:01 PM – 3:00 PM	Closing	Community Coordinator

Conclusions

Extracting from the findings, the researcher drew out the following conclusion:

1. Level of Implementation towards Corporate Social Responsibility of the mining corporation demonstrates a highly satisfactory level of CSR implementation, with stakeholders particularly appreciating the economic and legal responsibilities. The provision of job opportunities and adherence to legal standards like the Philippine Mining Act receive the highest ratings, indicating that these areas significantly contribute to stakeholder satisfaction. The corporation's efforts in ethical and philanthropic responsibilities are also well-regarded, highlighting its active role in addressing social issues and improving community infrastructure. Overall, the high satisfaction levels reflect the corporation's strong commitment to fulfilling its social responsibilities, which is crucial for maintaining trust and enhancing its reputation.
2. Impact on Community Development through CSR initiatives of the mining corporation have a substantial positive impact on various aspects of community

development. Health initiatives, such as medical missions, and educational programs, like scholarships, are highly valued by stakeholders for their effectiveness in addressing immediate needs and promoting long-term development. Livelihood programs and public utilities support further underscore the corporation's role in enhancing community safety, economic activities, and disaster preparedness. The highest impact is noted in the socio-cultural domain, emphasizing the importance of cultural preservation and community cohesion. These findings suggest that the corporation's CSR activities significantly contribute to the socio-economic advancement and well-being of the community.

3. Challenges in CSR Implementation despite the overall positive perception, several challenges hinder the effectiveness of CSR implementation. Economic assistance is perceived as insufficient due to selection biases and issues with employment contracts, indicating a need for more equitable and transparent processes. Awareness of legal responsibilities is limited outside immediate areas, highlighting the need for better communication strategies. Ethical challenges, including delayed salaries and inconsistent standards, and philanthropic issues related to the distribution of assistance during calamities, suggest areas for improvement in outreach and ethical practice adherence.
4. Variance in CSR Implementation that the significant difference in the level of CSR implementation perceived by indicates variability in how CSR activities are experienced across different areas. This suggests that while some aspects of CSR are highly effective, others may require further attention and improvement to ensure uniform satisfaction.
5. Variance in CSR Impact on Community Development that there is lack of significant difference in the perceived impact of CSR on community development suggests that stakeholders generally view the impact of CSR activities uniformly. This implies a consistent approach to CSR efforts across different community development aspects, contributing to stable and sustained benefits.
6. Correlation between CSR Implementation and Community Development that a positive correlation between CSR implementation and community development indicates that as CSR efforts increase, the positive impact on community development also rises. This relationship underscores the importance of sustained and enhanced CSR activities to promote greater socio-economic advancement within the community.

Recommendations

Based on the preceding findings and conclusion, the following recommendations are presented:

To enhance the effectiveness of its CSR initiatives, *Philsaga Mining Corporation* should consider several key actions. First, the corporation needs to enhance its economic assistance programs by addressing selection bias in financial aid distribution. Implementing transparent and equitable processes will ensure that all deserving individuals receive support, especially during calamities. Additionally, improving employment contracts to better meet employees' needs and address issues related to job security and benefits is crucial. Second, increasing awareness and communication is essential. Developing comprehensive communication strategies will help raise awareness about CSR programs in nearby cities and barangays. This effort can include regular community meetings, informative materials, and collaboration with local leaders to ensure a wider reach and understanding of the corporation's legal responsibilities and CSR initiatives. Third, improving ethical standards within the corporation is necessary. Ensuring timely payment of salaries and adherence to ethical standards across all operations, coupled with regular training sessions on ethical practices and a robust monitoring system, will help maintain high ethical standards and employee satisfaction. Lastly, strengthening philanthropic outreach is important. Enhancing outreach efforts to ensure that all community members are informed about and can benefit from philanthropic activities requires better coordination with local organizations and the use of multiple communication channels to disseminate information about assistance programs. This means by implementing these proposed frameworks for monitoring and controls to address the challenges and ensure effective CSR implementation. This framework will provide clear, actionable goals for implementing and maintaining CSR projects, ensuring that all beneficiaries receive the intended benefits and that CSR efforts remain transparent, equitable, and impactful. Further, *Philsaga Mining Corporation* can significantly improve the impact and perception of its CSR initiatives

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This present study subscribes to the principles of voluntary participation in research, implying that the respondents and key informants might withdraw from this research at any time. Informed consent, which means that the respondent must at all

times, be well informed about the research process and purposes and should give consent to his/her participation in this research.

Safety was exercised by the researcher to make sure that respondents and key informants should not be placed at risk of harm of any kind. Privacy entails that the confidentiality and anonymity of the both respondents and key informants should be protected at all times. Moreover, trust implies that the respondents and key informants must not be subjected to any acts of deception or betrayal in this research process or its published outcomes and has the right to know the conclusion of this study.

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REFERENCES

- Abuya, W.O., Odongo, G., 2020. Poisoned chalice or opportunity for positive impact? An analysis of the impact of ‘inherited’ corporate social responsibility (CSR) commitments in Kenya’s titanium mining industry. *Extr. Ind. Soc.* 7 (3), 1002–1010.
- Adorador, D. (2019). Dinagat mining firm wins responsible, ethical biz citation. (n.d.-b). Philippine News Agency. Retrieved from: <https://www.pna.gov.ph/articles/1071468>
- Ansu-Mensah, P., Marfo, E. O., Awuah, L. S., & Amoako, K. O. (2021). Corporate social responsibility and stakeholder engagement in Ghana’s mining sector: a case study of Newmont Ahafo mines. *International Journal of Corporate Social Responsibility*, 6(1). Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40991-020-00054-2>
- Asumah, A. (2015) “Effects of Corporate Social Responsibility on Community Development: A Case Study of AngloGold Ashanti Obuasi Mine.”
- Balog, K. (2019). Agile Organizations and Sustainability. *Sustainability, Environment, Safety* 2019, 111-121.
- Boutillier, R. G., & Thomson, I. (2011). Modelling and measuring the social license to operate: fruits of a dialogue between theory and practice. *Social Licence*, 1, 1-10.
- Chaloping, M. (2018). Collaboration towards social sustainability: the case of a mining corporation, its surrounding communities, and local government in Benguet, Philippines. Retrieved from: https://www.academia.edu/17148798/Collaboration_towards_social_sustainability_the_case_of_a_mining_corporation_its_surrounding_communities_and_local_government_in_Benguet_Philippines
- Chen, L. F., & Khuangga, D. L. (2021). Configurational paths of employee reactions to corporate social responsibility: An organizational justice perspective. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 28(1), 389-403.
- Ericsson, M., & Löf, O. (2019). Mining’s contribution to national economies between 1996 and 2016. *Mineral Economics*, 32(2), 223-250
- Frederiksen, T., 2019. Political settlements, the mining industry and corporate social responsibility in developing countries. *Extr. Ind. Soc.* 6 (1), 162–170.
- García-Sánchez, I. M., Hussain, N., Aibar-Guzmán, C., & Aibar-Guzmán, B. (2022). Assurance of corporate social responsibility reports: Does it reduce decoupling practices?. *Business Ethics, the Environment & Responsibility*, 31(1), 118-138.
- Gabriel, J., & Kobani, D. (2022). Indigenization of Corporate Social Responsibility Practices: Recipe for Community Development in Nigeria. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/360756707_indigenization_of_corporate_social_responsibility_practices_recipe_for_community_development_in_nigeria
- Hennink, M., Hutter, I., & Bailey, A. (2020). *Qualitative research methods*. Sage.
- Knutsen, A. Kotsadam, E.H. Olsen, T. Wig.(2017). Mining and local corruption in Africa *Am. J. Pol. Sci.*, 61 (2), pp. 320-334
- Kumar, A., Gupta, J., & Das, N. (2022). Community resilience, Corporate Social Responsibility and local economic development: The case of coal mining in India. *The Extractive Industries and Society*, 11, 101120. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.exis.2022.101120>

- Kumari, ., Schrawat, ., & Sharma,. (2017). Corporate Social Responsibility Practices and their Impact on the community: A case study of Anibuja Cement Ltd. Retrived from https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Anil-Sehrawat2/publication/312221012_Corporate_Social_Responsibility_Practices_and_Their_Impact_on_the_Community_A_Case_Study_of_Ambuja_Cement_Ltd/inks/58a27a3f92851c7fb4c1c85b/Corporate-Social-Responsibility-Practices-and-Their-Impact-on-the-Community-A-Case-Study-f-Ambuja-Cement-Ltd.pdf
- Kurowski, M., & Huk, K. (2021). Selected aspects of corporate social responsibility in the industry related to the production and supply of energy. *Energies*, 14(23), 7965.
- League of Corporate Foundations (LCF).(2010).[Online] Retrieved from: <http://www.lef.org.ph> (Accessed:17th October 202.)
- Licud-ambeguia, F. (2023). *Cognizance Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, Vol.3, Issue.11, November 2023, pg. 58-97. Retrieved from: <https://cognizancejournal.com/vol3issue11/V3I1106.pdf>
- Licud-ambeguia, F. (2023). Enhancing mining community services through corporate social responsibility and social development management strategies. Retrieved from:https://www.researchgate.net/publication/376074286_enhancing_mining_community_services_through_corporate_social_responsibility_and_social_development_management_strategies
- Mbilima, F., 2021. Extractive industries and local sustainable development in Zambia: the case of corporate social responsibility of selected metal mines. *Resour. Policy* 74,101441.
- Millington, R., & Darnell, S. (Eds.). (2019). *Sport, development and environmental sustainability*. Routledge.
- Muthuri, J. & Gilbert, V. (2018). An Institutional Analysis of Corporate Social Responsibility in Kenya. *Journal of Business Ethics* 98 (3):467-483. Retrived from <https://philpapers.org/rec/MUTAIA-2>.
- National Economic and Development Authority. Retrieved from <http://neda.gov.ph>
- Philsaga Mining Corp. Retrieved from <https://www.philsaga.com>
- Phiri, O., Mantzari, E., & Gleadle, P. (2019). Stakeholder interactions and corporate social responsibility (CSR) practices: Evidence from the Zambian copper mining sector. *Accounting, Auditing & Accountability Journal*, 32(1), 26-54
- Pimentel, J. (2010). A note on the usage of Likert Scaling for research data Practices and their Impact on the Community: A case study of Anibuja Cement Ltd. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Anil-Sehrawat2/publication/312221012_Corporate_Social_Responsibility_Practices_and_Their_Impact_on_the_Community_A_Case_Study_of_Ambuja_Cement_Ltd/inks/58a27a3f92851c7fb4c1c85b/Corporate-Social
- Porubčinová, M. (2020). Corporate Social Responsibility as a Part of Business Strategy in the Context of Sustainable Development. 74, 04020. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1051/shsconf/20207404020>
- Rela, I. Z., Awang, A. H., Ramli, Z., Taufik, Y., Sum, S. M., & Muhammad, M. (2020). Effect of corporate social responsibility on community resilience: empirical

- evidence in the nickel mining industry in Southeast Sulawesi, Indonesia. *Sustainability*, 12(4), 1395. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12041395>
- Sari, S., & Setiahadi, R. (2019). How important CSR to mining companies: Empirical case in Indonesia. *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, 347(1), 012121. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/347/1/012121>
- Sering, M. L. (2014). Corporate Social Responsibility of the Two Mining Companies in Surigao del Sur, Philippines. Retrieved from <https://www.smrj.sdssu.edu.ph/index.php/SMRJ/article/view/42>
- Shirasu, Y., Kawakita, H., 2021. Long-term financial performance of corporate social responsibility. *Glob. Finance J.* 50, 100532.
- Straka, M., Khouri, S., Lenort, R., Besta, P. 2020. Improvement of logistics in manufacturing system using simulation modelling: A real industrial case study. *Advances in Production Engineering & Management*, 15(1), 18-30.
- Surówka, M., Popławski, Ł., Fidlerová, H. 2021. Technical Infrastructure as an Element of Sustainable Development of Rural Regions in Małopolskie Voivodeship in Poland and Trnava Region in Slovakia. *Agriculture*, 11(2), 141.
- Yousefian, M., Bascompta, M., Pera, L. S., & Sánchez, C. V. (2023). Corporate social responsibility and economic growth in the mining industry. *The Extractive Industries and Society*, 13, 101226. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.exis.2023.101226>
- Yulianita, N. Nurrahmawati, N., & Wiwitan, T. (2018). Implementation of Corporate Social Responsibility Framework in Mining Companies. *Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research*, volume 307. Retrieved from: <https://www.atlantis-press.com/article/55915318.pdf>
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